

PEER- REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education Research
Journal (AMIERJ)
ISSN 2278-5655***

Impact Factor :0.948

Bi-Monthly

VOL - II

ISSUES - V

[2013-14]

**Chief-
Editor:**

**U b a l e
A m o l
B a b a n**

[Editorial/Head Office: 108, Gokuldharm Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near TV Towar,Badlapur, MS

**SOCIO-ACADEMIC PROFILE OF ELEMENTARY TEACHER EDUCATORS
WORKING IN DIETs OF NCT DELHI**

-Ms Veena Devi Trivedi

Abstract:

Socio-economic status of an individual determines his relative standing in the society he lives in, in terms of his material belongings and cultural possessions along with the degree of respect, power or influence he wields and consequently making it an important aspect to be known on the other hand having a good academic career is a requisite of a teacher or teacher educator. Academically qualified and professionally interested teacher-educators can train the trainees efficiently and impart them due and required knowledge, skills and training. Therefore this piece of research brings a status of the teacher educators working in DIETs of NCT Delhi in terms of their socio academic profile.

Key Words: Profile; Academic Career; Socio Economic Status; Elementary Teacher Educators.

1: Introductory Remarks

1.1: International Perspective on Education: Need for Paradigm Shift in Education

A homogenous web of enlightened creativity and in hindered progress is possible by making the education of all levels to be able to achieve its set /affixed objectives. Therefore there is need for a paradigm shift in educational philosophy, policies and programmes at the global scale as already called by Jacques Delors, President UNESCO International Commission on Education for the twenty first century. Prior to it requires a comprehensive assessment of the transformation and upheavals in the global society due to population explosion, environmental hazards, communication technologies and information systems, unbridled growth of capitalism

and materialism, serious gaps between the developed and developing societies and collapse of value systems across the globe. It is evident that the contours of the knowledge based society are emerging fast. The citizen of tomorrow has to face challenges in every sphere social, political, economic, and cultural therefore educating each and every young one around the globe with at least basic skills of knowledge and understanding becomes responsibility of every country, society and community. In the context of "Education for All" which declares that everyone has a right to education its aim is to give everyone a chance to learn and benefit from basic education not as an accident of circumstance or as a privilege, but as a right. The aspiration of making education available to all is not new. More than two hundred years ago, Adam Smith argued for universal education on the grounds of public order and the preservation of freedom. By the mid-20th century, education was enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as: "Everyone has a right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit." As an international initiative, Education for All (EFA) was first launched in Jomtien, Thailand in 1990 to bring the benefits of education to "every citizen in every society."

1.2: Indian Scenario on Education:

Independent India got a system of education which was not only quantitatively small but also characterized by structural imbalances. Only fourteen per cent of the population was literate and only one child out of three had been enrolled in primary school. As education is vitally linked with the totality of the developmental processes the reform and restructuring of the educational system was recognized as an important area of state intervention. The need for a literate population and universal education for all children in the age group of 6-14 was recognized as a crucial input for nation building and was given due consideration in the Constitution as well as in successive Five Year Plans. The National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986, revised in 1992, resolved to achieve the goal of 'Universalization of Elementary Education' by the turn of the century, emphasizing three aspects: universal access and enrolment; universal retention up to 14 years of age, and to bring about substantial improvement in the quality of education to enable all children to achieve essential levels of learning. The Policy set the goal of decentralized planning and management of elementary education. This thinking led to

the 73rd and 74th constitutional amendments that provide for decentralization of the activities and facilitate transfer of power and participation of the local self-government institutions or the Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs). In *Unikrishnan vs. State of Andhra Pradesh* (Writ Petition No.607 of 1992), Supreme Court held that citizens of this country have the fundamental right to education and the said right flows from Article 21 of the Constitution. This right is, however, not an absolute right. Every child/citizen of this country has the right to free education until he/she completes the age of fourteen years. Thereafter, his/her right to education is subject to limits of the economic capacity and development of the State. This movement has culminated in the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009 notified on 27th August, 2009, popularly called RTE Act. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) was launched by the Government of India for achievement of Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) in a time bound manner, as mandated by 86th amendment to the Constitution of India making free and compulsory Education to the Children of 6-14 years age group, a Fundamental Right. After the success of SSA, pressure has increased on the secondary education sector. The Govt. of India is now moving towards universalization of secondary education, for which the RMSA (Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan) has been launched on the lines of SSA in a missionary mode. There is a move to extend the scope of RTE Act to the target group beyond 14 years of age.

1.2: Importance of Present Research Work

In the six surveys, so far taken together 319 studies have been conducted in the area of teacher, teaching and teacher education. Researchers working in this area have brought into their study a wide spectrum of variables such as selection procedures, curriculum for teacher education programmes, effect of innovative instructional procedures on teacher effectiveness; the institution, the process of admission, training, climate, administrative set up, the student-teacher relationship, the personal characteristics of teachers and practice schools. All these factors and quite a few more, are constantly at work in the real setting. In the context of teacher characteristics as mentioned in the Sixth Survey of Research in Education (1993-2000) 41 studies that have investigated in characteristics of teachers includes 30 studies conducted to make findings of the characteristics of primary teachers. Moreover, the role of a teacher is central in basic education. Nearly all issues, whether related to goals, learning achievement, organization of programmes or performance of the education system, involve an analysis of the

role of teachers, their behaviour, performance, remuneration, incentives and skills and how they are used by the system. The teacher is the pivot on which the entire system revolves. The concept of teacher is as facilitator, diagnostician, and helper and as a person who is genuinely concerned. A successful educational system can only work when its backbone i.e. the teacher is completely balanced. Someone has rightly remarked,

“As is the teacher, so is the nation”

The goal of “Education for All” demands a variety of challenging roles to be performed by the elementary teachers who can actively perform it only when they are prepared for it in their preservice education programmes. This responsibility lies on the shoulders of the elementary teacher educators. Therefore characteristics of teacher educators matters a lot. Reform, restructuring or overhauling of the elementary teacher education system is only possible when the understanding of the personal characteristics of the human resource is made, who are engaged in preparing elementary teachers. It has been rightly observed:

As is the teacher-educator, so are the teachers,

As is the teacher, so are the students and

As is the student, so is the nation.

Having a good academic career is a requisite of a teacher or teacher educator. Academically qualified and professionally interested teacher-educators can train the trainees efficiently and impart them due and required knowledge, skills and training. Moreover the teacher educators in DIETs are required to have a good academic career. Therefore, whether they possess the good academic record or not it becomes essential to be examined. Review of literature indicates that maximum studies conducted on teachers, pupil teachers or few on teacher educators are comparative or co-relational taking some or different variables. None of the studies intend to develop a socio-academic profile of elementary teacher-educators working in DIETs of NCT Delhi taking these variables at a time. The role of the teacher instructor in DIETs is expected to be no longer one of transmitting readymade knowledge to the learners but instead that of a designer and facilitator of learning experiences, a manager of instruction and learning resources, and an active contributor to the all round development of the learner.

1.3: Research Questions:

-What type of socio economic status elementary teacher educators possess those who are working in DIETs?

-What is their academic career?

1.4: Terms Defined:

Profile:

A set of different measures of an individual or a group .Each of which is expressed in the same unit of measure (Kerlinger 1964; p 614)

Teacher Educators:

Those persons who are engaged in imparting training to the Pre-service and in- service teachers are the teacher educators. In this investigation the elementary teacher educators working in DIETs are considered.

Socio-Economic Status:

Socio economic status (SES) is an economic and sociological combined total measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's or family's economic and social position in relation to others, based on income, education, and occupation.(Wikipedia,)

Academic Career:

Academic career refers to the educational and professional qualifications attained by the teacher- educators. It includes obtaining additional degrees or diplomas, writing books, articles and papers, reading books and journals, conducting research, membership of professional bodies and committees etc.

1.5: Objectives of the Research Work

The study intends to develop a socio-academic profile of elementary teacher-educators working in DIETs of NCT Delhi.

1.6:Research Perspective:

Reddy (1980) found that economic standard positively influenced the effectiveness of a teacher. **Krishna (1982)** found that teachers of high economic status were more satisfied than low economic status. **Shah K, (1982)** made a sociological study on socio-economic background of primary school teachers and studied their job satisfaction. Findings revealed that the educational status was ordinary and the teachers belonging to different religions indicated the hold of religion in spite of various forces of modernization. **Gopalacharyulu (1984)** found a positive and significant relationship between socio economic statuses of the secondary teacher trainees with their academic achievement. **Fuch. I (1997)** examined the relations between teacher's images of

teaching and their socio-economic status. The findings indicated that the Socio-Economic status was negatively related to the images of expository style images of teaching. RATE studies reported that 80% of education professors hold doctoral degree and about 80% had teaching experience in elementary /secondary schools. The weekly workload of professors consisted of 60% teaching, 22% service and 15% scholarship. Over the years the RATE category system had expanded from teaching, service and scholarship. Over the years the RATE category system had expanded from teaching, service and scholarship to an eight category system that is preparation for conducting classes, teaching, research, offering advice, administration, proper formation of committees, in service education, supervision of student teachers and consultative work with elementary and secondary school teachers. Mehmet Ustuner, Hasan Demirtas and Melike Comert (2009) found a significant difference in the socio economic status (SES) of the neighborhood and family they live in with respect to their teaching attitude. Woodman (1999) also showed that the socio-economic status of the learners has a significant positive effect on their academic performance.

Methodology Adopted:

Random Sampling was done and a total of 42 sample subjects were selected randomly out of DIETs functional in Delhi.

Table : Showing Sample Distribution of the Sample Subjects Selected from DIETs in National Capital Territory (NCT) Delhi

S. No.	DIET	Total No. of Teacher Educators
1	Darya Ganj	11
2	Pitampura	08
3	Keshavpuram	07
4	Moti Bagh	07

- Reading books and journals,
- Conducting research,
- Membership of Professional bodies/Committees/Social Organization

The distribution of sample subjects into different levels of socio-economic status in NCT Delhi has been shown as under in table 4.81

Table: The Distribution of Sample Subjects into Different Levels of Socio-Economic Status in NCT Delhi

S. No.	Levels	F	%
1	Lower Middle	Nil	Nil
2	Middle	19	45
3	Upper Middle	16	38
4	High Class	7	17
	TOTAL	42	100

Table depicts the results as:

- 45% of the total sample subjects working in NCT Delhi lie under the category of ‘Middle Socio-Economic Class’ when their socio-economic status is considered.
- 38% of sample subjects lie in the category of ‘Upper Middle Socio-Economic Class’ followed by
- 17% of the sample subjects were found to be under the category of ‘High Socio Economic Class’.
- None of the teacher educators are in the category of ‘Lower Middle Class’ when their socio economic status is considered in NCT Delhi.

Graph: Showing the Distribution of Sample Subjects into Different Levels of Socio-Economic Status in NCT Delhi

Table: Distribution of Sample Subjects into Different Domains of Academic Career in NCT Delhi

Areas	Levels	f	%
Edu. & Prof. Qualifications	Masters with Prof. Degree	25	60
	Masters with Research Degree	17	40
	Any Other	NIL	NIL
Add. Qualifications Attained	Masters Degree	07	17
	Research Degree	12	29

	Any other	04	10
Publications	Having Publications	26	62
	Not having Publications	16	38
Reading Academic Literature	Always	38	90
	Often	04	10
Research Project Undertaken	Research Project Completed	14	33
	Research Project Going On	22	52
	Not Yet Undertaken Research Project	06	14
Membership of any Professional body/Committee/Organization	Having Membership	26	62
	Not Having Any Membership	16	38

Table depicts the result of academic career of the sample subjects in NCT Delhi as -60% of sample subjects have masters with professional degree, 40% have masters with research degree like M. Phil or Ph. D. In additional qualifications attained after joining the institute 17% gained masters degree in any other subject apart from their own subject. Mostly these subjects were from arts and humanities group.29 % attained research degree like M. Phil or Ph.D. in any subject. When asked about the publications 62% revealed that they have got publications which ranged from 1 to 6 in number. 38% were not having any publications as shown in table and graph 4.89. In case of reading academic literature which is part of their academic growth 90% accepted that they always read academic literature for updating themselves whereas 10% often read the academic literature for their academic updation.33% of sample subjects have completed one or the other research projects which were action research only whereas 52% have undertaken the projects which were minor projects only and action research as well which the sample subjects have to essentially undertake.14% were not working for any type of research projects.62% of sample subjects were having membership of any professional body which ,committee or any social organizations which included teacher’s and teacher educators associations and social clubs also whereas 38% were not having any membership of any professional body ,committee or any social organizations as shown in graph

Graph Showing the Distribution of Sample Subjects into Different Domains of Academic Career in NCT Delhi

4.90 Showing the Distribution of Sample Subjects into Different Domains of Academic

Conclusions: It is on the administrators, planners of the education and the educators to fully support and encourage the elementary teacher educators who prepare the elementary teachers who are the backbone of the entire educational system. There should not be any type of compromise in selection of the human resources who are engaged in teacher preparation at all levels more specifically at elementary level. There is an urgent need for dynamism , creativity ,innovation and teacher educators own experience in teacher preparation to improve in turn the profile of teacher educators at all aspects and dimensions and in all areas of their professional education as teacher educators.

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